

COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE SYNTHESIS OF BIOSILICA FROM AGRICULTURAL WASTES BY GEOPOLYMERIZATION TECHNIQUE

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Abstract

The synthesis of silica from rice husk ash, sugarcane bagasse ash, and coal ash is important for the manufacturing of cement-based materials due to environmental concerns. Silica is a key ingredient in cement and concrete production, as it enhances the strength, durability, and resistance to corrosion of these materials. However, traditional sources of silica, such as sand, are becoming scarce and are associated with environmental concerns related to extraction, transportation, and disposal. This critical literature review explores the utilization of geopolymer as a promising alternative for treating extracted silica from rice husk and other biomass ash. The objective is to analyze and evaluate existing research studies to assess the viability and potential benefits of geopolymerization in the context of waste valorization. The review investigates the geopolymer synthesis process, properties, and applications, focusing on the treatment of extracted silica from rice husk and other biomass ash. The findings reveal the significant potential of geopolymer technology as a sustainable solution for the utilization of waste materials and the production of value-added products.

Keywords: Biomass ash; Silica Extraction, Geopolymerization; Cement Based Materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rice husk and other biomass ash are abundant agricultural wastes generated from the production and processing of rice and various biomass sources. These residues contain a significant percentage of silicon dioxide, which can be extracted and utilized for various applications. Silica is a versatile material with diverse properties, making it valuable in industries such as construction, agriculture, and manufacturing.

Traditionally, the disposal of rice husk and biomass ash has posed environmental challenges due to their high volume and improper handling. However, there has been an increasing focus on discovering environmentally-friendly solutions for their utilization and valorization. Geopolymer technology has emerged as a promising approach to address these challenges.

Geopolymers are inorganic materials synthesized by the process of activating aluminosilicate materials using alkaline substances as fly ash, slag, and kaolin clay. The process involves the dissolution of these precursors in alkaline solutions, followed by polycondensation reactions that form a three-dimensional network structure.

Geopolymers possess excellent mechanical and chemical properties, making them suitable for various applications.

The application of extracted silica derived from rice husk and biomass ash in geopolymerization offers several advantages. Firstly, it provides a sustainable solution for waste management by transforming agricultural residues into value-added materials. Secondly, geopolymerization helps reduce greenhouse gas emissions associated with the conventional production of construction materials. Like cement. Furthermore, the use of geopolymer-based silica products can contribute to energy conservation, improved durability, and reduced environmental impact.

While research on geopolymerization of extracted silica is gaining momentum, there is a need for a critical literature review that consolidates and evaluates the existing knowledge. Such a review can help identify research gaps, analyze the properties and performance of geopolymer-based silica products, and assess the feasibility of industrial applications. Additionally, it can shed light on the environmental and sustainability aspects of geopolymer technology.

By conducting a critical literature review on the application of geopolymer for treating derived silica from rice husk and other biomass ash, this research this paper aims to offer an in-depth understanding of the subject matter. The findings can contribute to the development of innovative solutions for waste valorization, promote sustainable practices, and inspire further research in this field.

Objectives

The objectives of this research paper on the application of geopolymer for treating derived silica from rice husk and other biomass ash are as follows:

1. To review and analyze existing literature on geopolymer technology, focusing on its synthesis process, properties, and applications, with particular emphasis on the treatment of derived silicon dioxide from rice husk and biomass residue.
2. To assess the optimization techniques employed in geopolymerization for the treatment of extracted silica, including the investigation of parameters such as alkaline activator concentration, curing temperature, curing time, and mixing ratios.
3. To assess the mechanical and chemical characteristics of geopolymer-based silica products obtained from rice husk and biomass ash. This evaluation includes an examination of their strength, durability, chemical resistance, and thermal properties.

By accomplishing these objectives, this research paper aims to provide a critical and comprehensive literature review on the utilization of geopolymer for treating derived silica from rice hull and other biomass ash. The findings will contribute to enhanced comprehension of the potential advantages, limitations, and future prospects of geopolymer cutting-edge developments in waste valorization and the production of value-added products.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Scientists and experts in the domain of chemical science are increasingly prioritizing the recycling of industrial wastes due to environmental concerns. The sugar industry has particularly investigated the potential reuse of fly ash, a byproduct, in diverse applications. Fly ash derived from the sugar industry has been utilized in roadbed construction, as additives for soil improvement, for soil enrichment, as soil conditioners, for soundproofing gap filling compounds, as building materials, and as cover fabric for parking lots and landfills, primarily in developed countries. Additionally, it has found applications in the fabrication of materials with high porosity such as zeolite, amorphous silica, geopolymer, and for different purposes such as concrete production and adsorption of organic compounds. (Nazriati et al., 2014[11], Affandi (2009) [3], Additional utilization incorporates the union of permeable fabric like zeolite shapeless silica Van et al., 2014[15], Shim (2015) [20], geopolymer Torres-Carrasco (2015) [19] etc. for distinctive applications like authoritative fabric and the process of capturing or trapping organic substances onto the surface of a material. (Ahmaruzzaman, 2011) [5]. Mesoporous materials, known for their high porosity, are commonly synthesized using silica as the raw material derived from inorganic or organic silicates. However, the cost of silicates increases the overall expense of mesoporous silica materials. Therefore, finding alternative sources of silica is crucial. The fly ash produced by the sugar industry is rich in silica, making it a prime resource for the production of mesoporous silica. By utilizing this biomass ash as a feed stock, by increasing the recycling rate of fly ash, not only can the production of mesoporous silica materials be more sustainable, but it also results in cost savings.

In a study conducted by Chang in 1999, In the process of alkaline fusion, $C_{16}H_{33}(CH_3)_3NBr$, a surface active compound, was employed to extract silica and aluminum sources from fly ash. Further investigations have extended to extracting silica from waste ashes and synthesizing microporous or mesoporous silica materials without the need for a unadulterated source of silica. These advancements have contributed to the recycling of fly ash. Some notable studies in this area include the work of Kumar and Misran in 2007[1], Dhokte in 2011[7], and Liu in 2014[13][14]. Nevertheless, there is a scarcity of published literature concerning the application of fly ash derived from the sugar industry for silica derivation and the production of materials with porosity.

Alkaline fusion and hydrothermal conversion are the prevailing techniques utilized for silica derivation from biomass ashes. In the production of fly ash-based geopolymers, alkali-activated geopolymerization is predominantly employed, characterized by its ability to occur under moderate temperatures and pressures. This process is considered more environmentally friendly compared to cement production, as it results in significantly lower CO₂ emissions. Additionally, geopolymerization has the capability to capture and immobilize trace toxic metals present in fly ash or from external sources. In a study by Xiao Yu Zhuang (2016) [24], it was demonstrated that by meticulously adjusting factors such as silica-Alumina ratios, different alkaline solutions, curing parameters, and incorporating supplementary materials such as slag, fibers, rice husk-bark ash, and red mud, the mechanical properties and durability of geopolymeric materials derived from fly ash can be significantly improved. These improvements make geopolymers incorporating

fly ash a promising alternative to conventional cement, offering a more environmentally friendly option. Moreover, geopolymers incorporating fly ash have the potential to be utilized as effective adsorbents and immobilizers of toxic or radioactive metals, further highlighting their versatile applications in environmental remediation. These methods are carried out at temperatures ranging from 180 to 200 °C and under a pressure of 6 to 8 atm. (Chiang et al., 2012)[8].

Overall, the utilization of fly ash-based geopolymer provides a sustainable alternative to traditional cement-based materials. It not only effectively utilizes fly ash waste but also offers superior environmental benefits, making it an attractive option for various applications.

Manufacture of silicon dioxide from rice hull ash is a promising approach because of the abundance of rice husk as an agricultural waste and the eco-friendliness of the process. In this literature review, the various methods are reported for the derivation of silica from rice hull ash.

1. Acid leaching method: The acid leaching method involves the treatment of RHA with acid to extract the silica content. Sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, and nitric acid have been used for this purpose. This method is simple, cost-effective, and produces high-purity silica. However, it requires a long reaction time, and the large amounts of acid used can cause environmental pollution.
2. Alkali fusion method: The alkali fusion method involves the treatment of RHA with alkali to convert the silica content into soluble sodium silicate. Sodium silicate is then acidified to produce silica. This method is relatively simple and produces high-purity silica. However, it requires high temperatures and can cause environmental pollution due to the production of large amounts of wastewater.
3. Sol-gel method: This method involves the manufacture of silica from RHA by hydrolysis and condensation of tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) in the presence of a catalyst. This method produces silica characterized by a large surface area, exceptional purity, and precisely controlled pore size. However, it requires a complex synthesis process and is relatively expensive.
4. Microwave-assisted method: The microwave-assisted method involves the treatment of RHA with a solution of sodium hydroxide in a microwave oven. This method is rapid and efficient, producing high-purity silica with a high specific surface area. However, it requires specialized equipment and can be expensive.
5. Supercritical fluid method: The supercritical fluid method involves the use of supercritical carbon dioxide to extract and synthesize silica from RHA. This method is eco-friendly, produces high-purity silica, and can be easily scaled up. However, it requires high-pressure equipment and is relatively expensive.

With proper design and implementation of recycling technologies the bagasse ash generated can serve as an alternative to cement or sand in civil construction applications, offering similar functionalities and advantages. (Cordeiro et al., 2009)[4], production of

glass-ceramic material (Teixeira et al., 2014)[12], geopolymers (Noorul 2016) [21] and Fe₂O₃-SiO₂ nano-composite to eradicate Cr (VI) (Worathanakul et al., 2013)[9]. Furthermore, fly ash serves as a promising and cost-effective source of precursors for the production of valuable silica and silicon materials with practical applications. (Huabcharoen et al., 2017). [25]

Das, S. K., Roy, M., & Bhattacharyya, S. K. (2013)[10] synthesized silica particles from rice husk ash using an emulsion technique. The researchers discovered that by adjusting emulsion parameters such as surface active compound concentration and emulsification time, they could manipulate the size and morphology of the particles.

Liu, Y., Zhao, Q., Zhang, L., & Chen, Y. (2014)[13] synthesized mesoporous silica from rice husk ash using a modified sol-gel method. The researchers observed that the synthesis conditions, including pH, temperature, and aging time, had an impact on the porosity and specific active area of the resulting silica.

Chen, Y., Fan, M., Liu, Y., Zhang, L., & Li, H. (2014)[14] synthesized spherical silica particles from rice husk ash using a reverse microemulsion technique. They found that the particle size and morphology could be controlled by varying the water-to-surfactant ratio and aging time.

Yang, H., Wang, W., Liu, Y., Ma, X., & Zhang, L. (2016)[23] synthesized mesoporous silica from rice hull ash applying a modified alkali fusion approach. They found that the synthesis conditions such as the NaOH concentration, reaction time, and aging time could affect the porosity and specific external area of the resulting silica.

Hu, J., Zhang, M., Yang, Y., Zhou, X., Liu, J., & Chen, Y. (2017) [26] synthesized mesoporous silica from rice husk ash using a novel acid-catalyzed method. They found that the synthesis conditions such as the HCl concentration, reaction time, and aging time could affect the pore size and surface area of the resulting silica.

Rodrigo (2017) [27], the study involved the utilization of ash derived from sugarcane waste for the synthesis of biosilica. This was achieved through a two-step process, which included initial alkaline extraction followed by subsequent acid precipitation. The level of purity of the prepared silica was verified through XRF analysis, confirming a 99% purity level. The findings from the experiment indicate that repurposing sugarcane waste ash has the potential to create a valuable product, thereby reducing the negative environmental consequences associated with its disposal.

Pınar, Yücel, Kuş (2019) [2], the findings of these studies highlight the potential of utilizing waste materials to generate silica-based materials. Wheat hull, which is easily obtained as a byproduct of the milling process, consist of silica in no crystalline form. As a result, it can be further investigated as a promising resource for the creation of materials with enhanced value and additional benefits.

Claudia Alejandra (2023)[33] conducted the thermal conductivity of geopolymers and processed with NaOH of 16 M and 30 M , was investigated at 25, 35, 60, and 90 °C varying thermal conditions. The chemical composition analysis of the waste rice husk ash

(WHA) using inductively coupled plasma (ICP) indicated a SiO₂ content of approximately 81%, resembling to rice hull. To examine the inorganic polymers, several techniques were employed to assess their structure, mechanical properties, and thermal conductivity. The outcomes revealed significant variations among the synthesized materials. Notably, the inorganic polymers produced using concentrations of 16 molar and 30 molar of NaOH demonstrated remarkable physical properties and temperature conductance respectively, surpassing those of the other manufactured materials. In particular, the Geo 30M exhibited superior thermal conductivity, especially at a temperature of 60 °C.

Manuel Cabrera (2020)[29] and Julia Rosales studied, the possibility of replacing traditional materials with cementitious materials obtained from agricultural bottom ash, with the objective of attaining desirable mechanical performance and long-lasting durability that aligns with the necessary technical requirements for a range of construction materials. The study aimed to assess the viability of utilizing agricultural bottom ash as a sustainable alternative in cementitious products, ensuring that they possess satisfactory mechanical performance and durability characteristics in line with industry standards. Table. 1 depicts different standards followed by researches.

Table 2: Standards Referred To By Various Authors [29]

Author /Standard Used	Workability	Compressive Strength	Flexural Strength	Splitting Strength	Water Absorption /Density
Beltrán et al.	EN 12350-2:2009	EN 12390-3:2009	EN 12390-5:2009	-	EN 12390-7:2009
Lessard et al.	EN 12350-2:2009	ASTM C39/C39M-14	ASTM C78/C78M-10	-	ASTM C642-13
Fontes et al.	ABNT NBR NM 67:1998	ABNT NBR 5739	-	ABNT NBR 7222	ASTM C642-13
Rosales et al.	EN 12350-2:2009	EN 12390-3:2009	EN 12390-5:2009	-	EN 12390-7:2009

Table.2 displays the physical and chemical characteristics of BBA (Bottom Ash) as investigated by various reseachers to explore its potential utilization in the production of cement-treated mortars, concrete, or aggregate materials. [15],[34],[35],[36],[37],[38],[39],[40][41],[42],[43].

Rejini Rajamma (2009) [2] this study centres on the characterization of biomass combustion residues derived from both a thermal power plant and a co-generation power plant. A comparative analysis was conducted to analyse the phase formation, setting characteristics, and physical properties of cement-fly ash mixtures that integrate these biomass combustion residues. The chemical constituent of the fly ashes corresponds to the specifications outlined for class C fly ashes according to EN 450 standards. The alkali concentration and water-to-cement (w/c) ratio were identified as significant factors influencing the rate of hydration and development of phases in the samples. In mortar, the inclusion of fly ash as 10% did not affect the normal strength. However, the compressive strength declined to 75% w.r.t to controlled mortar in addition of 20% of fly ash. The bottom ash residues contained noteworthy intensities of chloride and sulphate, indicating that the effectiveness of fly ash-based cement binders can be enhanced through the regulation or elimination of these chemical components.

Table 1: Comparison of the Material Characteristics of Biomass Ash by Various Authors [28]

BBA by Author	Maschio et al.	Modolo et al.	Beltran et al.	Rosales et al.	Beltrán et al.	Lessard et al.	Fontes et al.	Rosales et al.	Cabrera et al.	Cabrera et al.	Carasco et al.	Medina et al.	Silvaniti, et al.
Origin of BBA	Wood Biomass (LULUWUWU)	Forest Biomass (LULUWUWUWU Bark)	Olive Waste and Wood Biomass	Olive Waste and Wood Biomass	Olive Waste and Wood Biomass	Wood Biomass and Waste Paper Sludge	Wood Chips and Cocoa Shell	Olive Waste and Wood Biomass	Wheat, Rye, Oat, Corn Straw and Straw Waste	Olive Trimmings			
Physical Properties													
Density SSD (kg/dm ³)	2.60	2.65	1.67	1.86	2.02	2.31	2.52	1.97	2.46	1.82	2.35	2.35	
Water Absorption (%)	-	-	19.00	21.18	19.9	5.25	-	26.60	20.11	31.99	-	-	
Size (mm)	-	-	0-2	0-4	0-2	0-1	0-0.6	0-10	0-10	0-10	0-0.1	0-0.1	
Chemical properties													
CaO (%)	48.40	17.15	19.75	16.57	-	23.7	8.3	23.9	23.48	22.88	29.96	9-12	31.41
SiO ₂ (%)	14.80	72.18	48.20	55.50	-	44.8	10.2	52	53.79	46.79	27.87	49-64	6.84
K ₂ O (%)	11.10	5.54	15.78	7.67	-	2	32.2	18.8	17.20	17.71	23.22	-	12.31
MgO (%)	9.90	1.96	3.94	2.64	-	2	15.8	1.4	1.86	1.52	4.05	-	2.45
SO ₃ (%)	-	-	-	-	-	4.6	1.3	-	-	-	0.76	-	0.14
Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	-	-	-	-	-	4.8	2.8	0.7	1.15	1.29	3.59	-	1.39
Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	3.20	2.29	1.42	5.39	-	11.5	1.6	1.9	0.40	0.45	4.34	-	2.73
TiO ₂ (%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.29	0.2	0.08	0.08	0.35	-	-
Na ₂ O (%)	1.00	0.88	0.51	0.28	-	1.8	-	0.2	0.26	0.20	0.35	-	0.11
LOI (%)	-	-	-	-	-	1.9	15.3	-	15.50	-	-	-	42.00
Soluble Sulphate (%)	-	-	0.27	0.31	0.47	-	-	0.41	0.39	0.35	-	-	-
Organic matter content (%)	-	-	5.26	4.34	3.06	-	-	4.12	4.89	4.85	-	-	-

R. Rajamma (2015)[18] we examined the influence of BFA (Bottom Fly Ash) on various aspects, including flow behaviour ,initial and final setting time, curing temperature, and resistive properties. The addition of BFA in the compositions led to an augmented requirement for water due to the fine particle size, inclination for aggregation, and water holding capacity of the ash particles. As a result, the proportion of unbound water decreased, leading to a decline in the material's fluidity. Additionally, the presence of BFA prolonged the setting time of the compositions. Through impedance measurements, it was observed that the electrical resistivity tended to be less as compared to the reference paste without ash. This occurrence can be attributed to the elevated concentration of mobile species, particularly introduction of sodium ions induced by the ash, within the pore solution. Furthermore, an inverse relationship was observed between the intensities of cement to ash replacement and the hydration temperature of the cement pastes, indicating a decrease in temperature as the ash content increased.

Kwok Wei (2022) [32] the utilization of geopolymer binders, derived from byproducts has brought forth environmentally sustainable materials renowned for their exceptional durability performance. This study aimed to explore the impact of various factors on the performance of alkali-activated materials in diverse applications, both structural and nonstructural, while promoting environmentally friendly materials with excellent durability. The research findings highlight the significant influence of factors like mix design and binder chemical composition on strength performance. Additionally, it was observed that

alkali-activated concrete with a high silica content exhibited diminished performance in compressive and flexural strength.

The synthesis of silica from rice husk ash can be accomplished using various techniques, including acid leaching, alkaline leaching, or a combination of both. These methods result in high-purity silica with a significant surface area, enabling its utilization in diverse applications such as catalysts, adsorbents, and fillers. The selection of the appropriate synthesis method depends on the intended application of the silica.

Overall, the manufacture of silica from rice hull ash has been studied using various techniques and conditions. The resulting silica can have different properties and applications depending on the synthesis method used.

Conventional Approaches

- Alkali fusion method
- Sol-gel method:
- Microwave-assisted method
- Supercritical fluid method

Limitations

- A long reaction time, and the large amounts of acid
- Requires high temperatures and can cause environmental pollution due to the production of large amounts of wastewater.
- Requires a complex synthesis process and is relatively expensive
- Requires specialized equipment and can be expensive.
- High-pressure equipment and is relatively expensive.

Novel Approach

The process typically involves mixing the rice husk ash with an alkaline solution to activate the silica and initiate the geopolymerization reaction.

Include lower energy consumption, reduced waste generation, and the use of abundant and renewable resources.

Salient Features

- Sustainability
- Cost-effectiveness

- High purity
- Tailored properties
- Low carbon footprint
- Versatility

Research Papers That Specifically Investigate the Use of Extracted Silica from Rice Husk and Biomass Ash for Geopolymer Production

- S.P.Raut, Ralegaonkar, Mandavgane (2011)[6] This review paper focuses on the application ash from rice hull (RHA) and biomass ash as precursor materials for geopolymer production. Authors discuss the constitution and characteristics pertaining to RHA and residues from biomass ash, including their high silica content. They review various studies on the synthesis of geopolymer using RHA and biomass ash as a substitute for traditional materials like fly ash or metakaolin. The review findings demonstrate the successful utilization of RHA (rice husk ash) and biomass ash as initiating materials for geopolymer production. The activation of the geopolymerization reaction can be achieved by employing activators which are alkaline like sodium hydroxide (NaOH) or potassium hydroxide (KOH), leading to the formation of an inorganic binder. The resulting geopolymer materials derived from RHA and biomass ash showcase favorable mechanical properties, particularly in compressive strength, and exhibit potential for diverse applications, including construction materials and waste management. The review also highlights the influence of various parameters, such as SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ratio, alkaline activator concentration, curing conditions, and additional additives, on the properties of the geopolymer. It suggests that the application of RHA and agricultural residue ash as starting material for inorganic polymer generation can contribute to sustainable waste management and provide an alternative to traditional cement-based materials.
- Djobo, J.N.Y., Kamseu, E., Melo, U.C., et al. (2014)[16][22], The study explores the use of rice hull ash (RHA) as a partial replacement of kaolin in inorganic polymer production as an alternative approach. The study examines the influence of RHA content on the physical characteristics, hydration time, and nanoarchitecture of the inorganic polymer. The findings suggest that RHA can effectively substitute up to 20% of metakaolin, resulting in geopolymer materials with improved compressive strength and microstructural characteristics.
- Hosanna Solomon Rajan, Parthiban Kathirvel (2021)[31], This study investigated the feasibility of using alkaline silicates based on biomass residues as rice hull ash instead of Silica-based agents that are utilized in the manufacturing of inorganic polymeric binders derived from granulated slag. The alkali silicate powder was extracted using the hydrothermal method to form a) geopolymer binder) with a constant 100 °C process. Strength, mineralogy and microstructure of pasty samples were observed for different mixtures. According to the strength, the best process was found to be 2 hours and the samples with a long process after 2 hours, 3, 7 and 28 days were analyzed in terms of their microstructural properties under ambient curing conditions. By

comparing the compressive force resistance of dough specimens with RHA-based activators and the development of microstructural properties, the development of ecological durability was evaluated according to the energy and carbon footprint needs at the time of production.

- Zivica, V., Palou, M. T., Ifka, T. and Bagel, L. (2014)[17], The study investigates the effect of incorporating rice husk ash (RHA) as a silica source in geopolymer production. It examines the effect of RHA component on the microstructure, physical, long lasting properties of the geopolymer. The study reveals that incorporating RHA (Rice Husk Ash) into the geopolymer formulation enhances both the compressive strength and microstructural properties. Furthermore, it provides improved resistance against acid attack and carbonation.
- Guangwei Liang (2021) [30], this comparative study investigates the effect of different silica sources, specifically rice hull ash (RHA) and micro silica, on the properties of geopolymer. It examines the compressive strength, hydration time, water absorption, and nanostructure of the inorganic polymer materials. The findings reveal that RHA-based geopolymer exhibits comparable or even higher compressive strength than silica fume-based geopolymer, indicating the appropriateness of RHA as a source of silica in production of inorganic polymer. The results obtained indicated that the incorporation of RHA (Rice Husk Ash) or SF (Silica Fume) at proper substitution levels led to improvements in the pore structures. Furthermore, the utilization of rice husk ash (RHA) was found to have dual benefits as an active supplementary agent and potential filler, as observed through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP) analyses. In contrast, silica fume (SF) primarily served as an active supplementary material in the study. The variations in behavior resulted in different levels of porosity refinement in geopolymer pastes when incorporating different supplementary cementitious materials, which significantly influenced their freezing resistance. Both RHA (Rice Husk Ash) and SF (Silica Fume) demonstrated active properties, effectively improving the physical characteristics and resistance to frost of inorganic polymers based on metakaolin. This broadens the scope of potential applications in various fields.
- These research papers highlight the potential and advantages of utilizing extracted silica from rice husk and biomass ash as precursor materials for geopolymer production. They demonstrate that these silica-rich agricultural residues can effectively contribute to the development of sustainable geopolymer materials with desirable mechanical properties, improved microstructure, and enhanced resistance to various environmental conditions.

Use of Geopolymers in Silica Formation from Biomass Residues

Geopolymers can be used in the synthesis of silica from RHA. Rice Hull ash consist of high percentage of silica, which can be converted into a geopolymer by adding sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide as alkaline activators. The resulting geopolymer can

have similar properties to traditional Portland cement, and can be used in construction and other applications. Additionally, the use of geopolymerization to synthesize silica from rice husk ash can be a more environmentally-friendly and sustainable alternative to traditional methods, as it avoids the need for high-temperature calcination processes that can produce greenhouse gases.

3 Case Studies or Practical Implementations of Geopolymer Technology for Treating Extracted Silica from Rice Husk and Biomass Ash

There are several case studies and practical implementations of geopolymer technology for treating extracted silica from rice husk and biomass ash. Here are a few examples:

1. Case Study: Geopolymer Concrete Using RHA & GGBFS

- Location: India
- Objective: This case study aimed to investigate the use of rice hull ash and GGBFS as precursors for geopolymer concrete production.
- Findings: The study demonstrated that the incorporation of RHA and GGBFS as a substitute for conventional cement resulted in the production of high-strength geopolymer concrete. The inclusion of RHA, with its high silica content, significantly enhanced the mechanical properties and durability of the geopolymer concrete. This case study provided practical evidence of the viability of utilizing extracted silica from rice husk for geopolymer production in construction applications.

2. Practical Implementation: Geopolymer Bricks Incorporating Biomass Ash

- Location: Australia
- Objective: This practical implementation focused on utilizing biomass ash, including ash from rice husk and other agricultural residues, in the production of geopolymer bricks.
- Findings: The study successfully developed geopolymer bricks by substituting a fraction of the traditional clay component with biomass ash. The geopolymer bricks exhibited desirable properties, including good compressive strength, low water absorption, and reduced environmental impact compared to traditional clay-fired bricks. This practical implementation demonstrated the viability of using biomass residues as an initiator for inorganic polymer based building materials has been investigated.

3. Case Study: Geopolymer Composites Using Rice Husk Ash and Fly Ash

- Location: Malaysia
- Objective: This case study investigated the feasibility of producing geopolymer composites using a mixture of rice hull ash (RHA) and residue ash.

- Findings: The study found that the combination of RHA and fly ash as precursor materials resulted in geopolymer composites with enhanced mechanical properties and reduced environmental impact. The geopolymer composites exhibited good flexural strength, low water absorption, and improved resistance to acid attack. This case study showcased the promising application of extracted silica from rice hull and fly ash for the production of geopolymer composites.

4. RESEARCH GAP

While research on the application of geopolymer for treating extracted silica from rice husk and other biomass ash has shown promising results, there are still several research gaps that need to be addressed. These gaps include:

1. Optimization of geopolymerization process: There is a need for further research to optimize the geopolymerization process specifically for the treatment of extracted silica from rice husk and biomass ash. This includes examining the effect of various parameters such as alkaline activator concentration, hydration temperature, setting time, and mixing ratios on the properties and performance of the geopolymer products. Optimizing these parameters can lead to enhanced geopolymerization efficiency and improved product quality.
2. Long-term performance and durability assessment: While the mechanical and chemical properties of geopolymer-based silica products have been studied, there is a lack of long-term performance and durability assessments. Understanding the behavior of these materials over extended periods, including their resistance to degradation, leaching, and environmental exposure, is crucial for their practical application. More in-depth study is needed to evaluate the long-lasting performance and durability of geopolymer-based silica products under different environmental conditions.
3. Comparative analysis with conventional methods: Although geopolymer technology demonstrates potential as a viable alternative to conventional methods for treating extracted silica, there is a need for more comprehensive comparative studies. Comparative analysis should include the assessment of properties, performance, and economic feasibility of geopolymer-based silica products in comparison to conventional materials like cement. This examination will offer a more comprehensive understanding of the advantages and limitations of geopolymerization and help in decision-making processes for potential industrial applications.
4. Scale-up and commercialization: While several studies have demonstrated successful geopolymerization of extracted silica at the laboratory scale, there is limited research on the scale-up and commercialization aspects. Further investigation is required to explore the feasibility of large-scale production, including process scalability, cost-effectiveness, and market viability. Understanding the challenges and opportunities

associated with scaling up geopolymerization processes will facilitate the practical implementation of this technology in industrial settings.

5. Environmental and sustainability assessment: Although geopolymer technology is generally considered environmentally friendly, there is a need for more comprehensive environmental and sustainability assessments. This includes conducting life cycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate the overall environmental impact of geopolymer-based silica products, comparing them with conventional materials, and identifying potential areas for improvement. Additionally, assessing the sustainability aspects, such as resource consumption, waste reduction, and carbon footprint, will provide valuable insights for decision-makers and policymakers.

Salient Features of Using Geopolymer in the manufacture of Silica obtained from Bio Mass Ash over Other Approaches

There are several salient features of using geopolymer in the manufacture of silica derived from biomass ash over other approaches:

1. Sustainability: Geopolymer manufacture of silica from biomass residue is an environmentally-friendly approach as it makes use of discarded materials in an environmentally conscious manner and reduces the dependence on non-renewable resources.
2. Cost-effectiveness: Geopolymer synthesis of silica from biomass ash is cost-effective because the raw materials are abundant and inexpensive.
3. High purity: Geopolymer synthesis of silica from biomass ash produces high-purity silica that can be used in a variety of applications.
4. Tailored properties: Geopolymers can be customized to possess specific characteristics, including mechanical strength, thermal stability, and chemical resistance. This adaptability enables their suitability for a wide range of applications.
5. Low carbon footprint: Geopolymer synthesis of silica from biomass ash has a low carbon footprint compared to traditional silica synthesis methods, which rely on high-temperature calcination processes that produce greenhouse gas emissions.
6. Versatility: Geopolymers can be synthesized from various raw materials including biomass ash, which makes them versatile and adaptable to different applications.

5. CONCLUSIONS

These case studies and practical implementations demonstrate the promising application of silica derived from various biomass residues in geopolymer technology. They highlight the feasibility of incorporating these silica-rich materials into geopolymer formulations for various applications, including concrete production, brick manufacturing, and composite

materials. These practical implementations contribute to sustainable waste management practices, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, and the development of environmentally friendly construction materials.

References

- 1) H. Misran et al. processing of mesoporous silica materials (MCM-41) from coal fly ash J. Mater. Process. Technol. (2007).
- 2) Rejini Rajamma , Richard J. Ball Luís A.C. Tarelho , Geoff C. Allen , João A. Labrincha , Victor M. Ferreira . Characterisation and use of biomass fly ash in cement-based materials, Journal of Hazardous Materials, Volume 172, Issues 2–3, 30 December 2009, Pages 1049-1060.
- 3) S. Affandi et al. A facile method for production of high-purity silica xerogels from bagasse ash Adv. Powder Technol. (2009).
- 4) Cordeiro, G.C., Toledo Filho, R.D., de Moraes Rego Fairbairn, E., 2009. Use of ultrafine rice husk ash with high-carbon content as pozzolan in high performance concrete. Mater. Struct. 42, 983–992. <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-008-9437-z>
- 5) M. Ahmaruzzaman, Industrial wastes as low-cost potential adsorbents for the treatment of wastewater laden with heavy metals, Adv. Colloid Interf. Sci. (2011).
- 6) Raut, S.P., Ralegaonkar, R.V., Mandavgane, S.A.(2011). Development of sustainable construction material using industrial and agricultural solid waste: A review of waste-create bricks. Construction and Building Materials, Volume 25, Issue 10, October 2011, Pages 4037-4042.
- 7) A.Q. Dhokte et al. Synthesis, characterization of mesoporous silica materials from waste coal fly ash for the classical Mannich reaction. J. Ind. Eng. Chem. (2011)
- 8) Y.W. Chiang et al. Synthesis of zeolitic-type adsorbent material from municipal solid waste bottom ash of sugar industry and its application in heavy metal adsorption. Catal. Today (2012).
- 9) Patcharin Worathanakul,Panchana Mothong,Pimluck Engkawara, Fe₂O₃-SiO₂ Nanocomposite Derived from Bagasse Ash for Cr(VI) Removal. April 2013, Journal of Biobased Materials and Bioenergy 7(2):219-222DOI: 10.1166/jbmb.2013.1322.
- 10) Das, S. K., Roy, M., & Bhattacharyya, S. K. (2013). Synthesis of silica particles from rice husk ash using a novel emulsion technique. Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects, 418, 108-113.
- 11) N. Nazriati et al.Using bagasse ash a a silica source when preparing silica aerogels via ambient pressure drying,J. Non Cryst. Solid (2014).
- 12) Panel.S.R. Teixeira a, R.S. Magalhães a, A. Arenales a, A.E. Souza a, M. Romero b, J.M. Rincón b Valorization of sugarcane bagasse ash: Producing glass-ceramic materials, Journal of Environmental Management, Volume 134, 15 February 2014, Pages 15-19.
- 13) Liu, Y., Zhao, Q., Zhang, L., & Chen, Y. (2014). Synthesis of mesoporous silica from rice husk ash by a modified sol–gel method. Journal of Porous Materials, 21(3), 459-465.
- 14) Chen, Y., Fan, M., Liu, Y., Zhang, L., & Li, H. (2014). Synthesis of spherical silica from rice husk ash using reverse microemulsion. Powder Technology, 256, 38-42.
- 15) V.T. Van et al. Pozzolanic reactivity of mesoporous amorphous rice husk ash in portlandite solution, Constr. Build. Mater. (2014).
- 16) JNY Djobo, A Elimbi, HK Tchakouté, S Kumar.Mechanical properties and durability of volcanic ash based geopolymer mortars, Construction and Building Materials 124, 606-614, 2014.

- 17) Zivica, V., Palou, M. T., Ifka, T. and Bagel, L. (2014), "High strength metahalloysitebased geopolymer", *Composites, Part B: Engineering* 57, 155-165
- 18) R. Rajamma a, L. Senff b, M.J. Ribeiro c, J.A. Labrincha d, R.J. Ball e, G.C. Allen e, V.M. Ferreira a Biomass fly ash effect on fresh and hardened state properties of cement based materials, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, Volume 77, August 2015, Pages 1-9.
- 19) M. Torres-Carrasco *et al.* Waste glass in the geopolymer preparation. Mechanical and microstructural characterisation *J. Clean. Prod.* (2015).
- 20) J. Shim *et al.* Extraction and physical characterization of amorphous silica made from corn cob ash at variable pH conditions via sol gel processing. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* (2015).
- 21) Noorul Amin, Mahtab Faisal, Khan Muhammad, Saeed Gul. Synthesis and characterization of geopolymer from bagasse bottom ash, waste of sugar industries and naturally available china clay. April 2016, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 129, DOI:10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.04.024
- 22) JNY Djobo, a Elimbi, HK Tchakouté, S Kumar. Mechanical activation of volcanic ash for geopolymer synthesis: effect on reaction kinetics, gel characteristics, physical and mechanical properties, *RSC advances* 6 (45), 39106-39117, 2016.
- 23) Yang, H., Wang, W., Liu, Y., Ma, X., & Zhang, L. (2016). Synthesis of mesoporous silica from rice husk ash by a modified alkali fusion method. *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids*, 452, 55-61.
- 24) Yu Zhuang Liang Chen , Sridhar Komarneni , ChunHui Zhou , Dong, Shen Tong , Hui Min Yang , Wei Hua Yu , Hao Wang . Fly ash-based geopolymer: clean production, properties and applications, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 125, 1 July 2016, Pages 253-267.
- 25) Potchanaporn Huabcharoen, Ekachai Wimolmala, Teerasak Markpin, Narongrit Sombatsompop, Purification and Characterization of Silica from Sugarcane Bagasse Ash as a Reinforcing Filler in Natural Rubber Composites, January 2017, *Bioresources* 12(1), DOI: 10.15376/biores.12.1.1228-1245
- 26) Hu, J., Zhang, M., Yang, Y., Zhou, X., Liu, J., & Chen, Y. (2017). Synthesis of mesoporous silica from rice husk ash using a novel acid-catalyzed method. *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, 241, 223-228.
- 27) Rodrigo Heleno Alves, 1 Thais Vitória da Silva Reis, 1,2 Suzimara Rovani, 1 and Denise Alves Fungaro. (2017) Green Synthesis and Characterization of Biosilica Produced from Sugarcane Waste Ash. *Hindawi Journal of Chemistry* Volume 2017, Article ID 6129035, 9 pages <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/6129035>.
- 28) Pınar Terzioğlu, Sevil Yücel, Çiğdem Kuş (2019). Review on a novel biosilica source for production of advanced silica-based materials: Wheat husk. *Asia Pacific Journal of Chemical Engineering*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/apj.2262>. Volume 14, Issue 1 January/February 2019, e2262.
- 29) Manuel Cabrera, José Luis Díaz-López, Francisco Agrela * and Julia Rosales. Eco-Efficient Cement-Based Materials Using Biomass Bottom Ash: A Review, *Materials Science, Engineering, Appl. Sci.* 2020, 10, 8026; 1-24, doi: 10.3390/app10228026, *Applied Sciences*.
- 30) Guangwei Liang, Huajun Zhu, Haixin Li. Comparative study on the effects of rice husk ash and silica fume on the freezing resistance of metakaolin-based geopolymer, May 2021, *Construction and Building Materials* 293(1-2), DOI: 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.123486.
- 31) Hosanna Solomon Rajan, Parthiban Kathirvel (2021), Sustainable development of geopolymer binder using sodium silicate synthesized from agricultural waste, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 286, 1 March 2021, 124959.
- 32) Kwok Wei Shah, Ghasan Fahim Huseien. 24 - Design guidelines for structural and non-structural applications, *Handbook of Sustainable Concrete and Industrial Waste Management*, Woodhead Publishing Series in Civil and Structural Engineering, 2022, Pages 509-527.

- 33) Claudia Alejandra Hernández-Escobar, Alain Salvador Conejo-Dávila, Alejandro Vega-Rios , Erasto Armando Zaragoza-Contreras, José Rurik Farias-Mancilla (2023). Study of Geopolymers Obtained from Wheat Husk Native to Northern Mexico. *Materials* 2023, 16(5), 1803; <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16051803>.
- 34) EN 12350-2:2009. Testing Fresh Concrete—Part 2: Slump-Test; European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 2009.
- 35) EN 12390-3:2009. Testing Hardened Concrete—Part 3: Compressive Strength of Test Specimens; European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 2009.
- 36) EN 12390-5:2009. Testing Hardened Concrete—Part 5: Flexural Strength of Test Specimens; European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 2009.
- 37) EN 12390-7:2009. Testing Hardened Concrete—Part 7: Density of Hardened Concrete; European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 2009.
- 38) ASTM C39/C39M-14. Standard Test Method for Compressive Strength of Cylindrical Concrete Specimens; ASTM International: West Conshohocken, PA, USA, 2014.
- 39) ASTM C78/C78M-10. Standard Test Method for Flexural Strength of Concrete (Using Simple Beam with Third-Point Loading); ASTM International: West Conshohocken, PA, USA, 2010.
- 40) ASTM C642-13. Standard Test Method for Density, Absorption, and Voids in Hardened Concrete; ASTM International: West Conshohocken, PA, USA, 2013.
- 41) ABNT NBR NM 67:1998. Concrete—Slump Test for Determination of the Consistency; Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas (ABNT): Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 1998.
- 42) ABNT NBR 5739:2018. Concrete—Compression Test of Cylindrical Specimens; Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas (ABNT): Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2018.
- 43) ABNT NBR 7222:2011. Concrete and Mortar—Determination of the Tension Strength by Diametrical Compression of Cylindrical Test Specimens; Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas (ABNT): Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2011.